

Additional List of the Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae, Piesmatidae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Tingidae (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) of Çankırı Province in Türkiye

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ABSTRACT: This study was carried out in the Çankırı province between 2013 and 2014. In this study, 48 species from 11 families (Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae, Piesmatidae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Tingidae) were recorded. 38 of these species are reported for the first time Heteroptera fauna of Çankırı.

KEY WORDS: Heteroptera, Fauna, Çankırı, Türkiye.

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INTRODUCTION

The Heteroptera is one of the largest and most diverse groups of insects. The order Hemiptera Linnaeus, 1758 ranks fifth in the world with 104.165 species after the

orders Coleoptera, Diptera, Lepidoptera and Hymenoptera (Zhang, 2011). Heteroptera Latreille, 1810 is a suborder of Hemiptera which contains 42.347 described species. Among these, there are 1.518 genera and

8.350 species in the Palearctic region (Henry, 2009). The number of species listed from the Palaearctic Region increased from 8.571 to 9.365 in the period with the publication of the original six volumes (1995-2013) (Aukema & Rieger, 1995; 1996; 1999; 2001; 2006; Aukem et al., 2013).

Studies on the Heteroptera in Türkiye, more than 1.500 Heteropteran species have been recorded so far which make up about 5% of all of its insect fauna. Among these, revealed are currently represented as Anthocoridae (41); Berytidae (24); Coreidae (50); Cydnidae (41); Lygaeidae (275); Nabidae (24); Piesmatidae (6); Reduviidae (65); Rhopalidae (30); Scutelleridae (40) and Tingidae (89) (Tezcan, 2020).

Türkiye has been known to possess a rich fauna of Heteroptera. Thus, many faunistic and systematic studies about the Heteroptera have been conducted by both foreign and native researchers in Türkiye. Some faunistic studies on this suborder in the Türkiye have been made by Horváth, 1883, 1901; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Tuatay et al., 1972; Aysev, 1974; Önder et al., 1984; Kıyak, 1990a, 1990b, 2000; Çam, 1993; Lodos et al., 1999; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Kıyak et al., 2004; Öz Saraç, 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2009, 2011a, 2011b; Dursun & Fent, 2009, 2017; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2010, 2011, 2013a, 2013b, 2014; Atlıhan et al., 2011; Fent,

2011; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Küçükbasmacı, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Asal, 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015a, 2015b, 2022, 2023; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi et al., 2018, 2021, 2022; Yazıcı, 2015a, 2015b, 2019, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c, 2023; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Özgen et al., 2021.

Çankırı is a transition region between Central Anatolia and Black Sea Region of Turkey. Therefore, in this transition area the diversity and abundance of insects is more because of its abundant variety of plants. According to initial records from Çankırı, 57 Heteropteran species were collected (Yazıcı et al., 2022). The aim of this study is to present new collection and biological data on Heteroptera in Çankırı. In this paper, 48 species of 41 genera belonging to 11 families from the suborder Heteroptera are recorded.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Heteroptera materials were collected from different localities in Çankırı province 2013-2014.

Samples were collected using traps and/or mouth aspirator. Collected samples were taken into pre-prepared kill bottles containing 70% alcohol and killed. The available specimens for the present study are deposited in Gazi University (Türkiye: Ankara).

RESULTS

In this study, 48 species of 41 genera belonging to 11 families from the suborder Heteroptera were recorded from Türkiye.

Family ANTHOCORIDAE Fieber, 1836

Subfamily Anthocorinae Fieber, 1836

Genus *Orius* Wolff, 1811

Subgenus *Heterorius* Wagner, 1952

Orius (Heterorius) minutus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Cimex minutus Linnaeus, 1758.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Atkaracalar, Yakalı, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; Center, Doğanstepe, 40°35'34"N, 33°36'50"E, 751 m, 23.VII.2013, ♂; Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀; Yeniyan, 40°26'39,8"N, 33°55'43,5"E, 702 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Köprülü, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.V.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, Yakadere, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bartın, Batman, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Iğdır, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Mardin, Niğde, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Zonguldak (Hoberlandt, 1956; Çam, 1993; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Yazıcı, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Pehlivan & Atakan, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Subgenus *Orius* Wolff, 1811

Orius (Orius) niger (Wolff, 1811)

Salda nigra Wolff, 1811; *Rhynarius obscurus* Hahn, 1832; *Anthocoris compressicornis* R.F. Sahlberg, 1848; *Anthocoris crassicornis* Perris, 1857; *Triphleps ullrichi* Fieber, 1860; *Anthocoris neglectus* Garbiglietti, 1869; *Orius* (s. str.) *niger aegyptiacus* Wagner, 1952.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Doğanstepe, 40°35'34"N, 33°36'50"E, 751 m, 23.VII.2013, ♀; Orta, Dodurga, 40°36'11"N, 33°00'18"E, 1351 m, 22.V.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bayburt, Batman, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Iğdır, Karaman, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Mardin, Niğde, Siirt, Şanlıurfa (Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 1984; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Kaplan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2019; Bolu, 2020; Pehlivan & Atakan, 2020; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Family BERYTIDAE Fieber, 1851

Genus *Metacanthus* A. Costa, 1843

Subgenus *Metacanthus* A. Costa, 1843

Metacanthus (Metacanthus) meridionalis (A. Costa, 1843)

Berytus meridionalis A. Costa, 1843; *Megalomerium pallidum* Fieber, 1859; *Cardopostethus fulvus* Jakovlev, 1875; *Metacanthus pusillus* (non Horváth, 1912): Linnavuori, 1960; *Metacanthus linnavuorii* Péricart, 1976; *Metacanthus linnavuorii* Štusák, 1977.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Orta, Derebayındır, 40°34'56"N, 32°59'50"E, 1389 m, 22.V.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Balıkesir, Mardin (Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun, 2016).

Family COREIDAE Leach, 1815

Subfamily Coreinae Leach, 1815

Genus *Centrocoris* Kolenati, 1845

Centrocoris variegatus Kolenati, 1845

Centrocoris variegata Kolenati, 1845; *Centrocarenus spiniger* var. *nigricans* Fieber, 1861; *Centrocoris variegatus* f. *convergens* Sienkiewicz in Stichel, 1959.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Tuzlu and Dede villages,

40°36'18"N, 33°40'36"E, 874 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Eldivan, Eldivan Mountain, 40°30'24,5"N, 33°30'28"E, 1132 m, 11.VII.2014, ♀, ♂; Çerkeş, return of Akbaş and Korakoca, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂, Ova, 40°47'27,6"N, 32°57'25,7"E, 1148 m, 20.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Artvin, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Bursa, Çorum, Denizli, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Konya, Manisa, Muğla, Sinop, Tokat (Tuatay et al., 1972; Öz Saraç, 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Şerban, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Dursun, 2016; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Genus *Enoplops* Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Enoplops disciger* (Kolenati, 1845)**

Coreus (*Palethrocoris*) *disciger* Kolenati, 1845.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Atkaracalar, Yakalı, 40°53'56"N, 33°8'51"E, 1210 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; Center, between Pehlivanlı and Alaçatı villages, 40°34'19" N, 33°52'18"E, 925 m, 26.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, ♂; Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀; Orta, İnkılap village, 40°34'48"N, 33°03' 41"E, 1290 m, 24.V.2014, ♀, ♂, Yuva village exit, 40°36'57"N, 33°01'36"E, 1306 m, 22.V.2014, ♀, ♂; Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Burdur, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Çorum, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, İzmir, Kars, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Manisa, Muğla, Muş, Niğde, Sivas, Tunceli (Kıyak, 2000; Öz Saraç & Kıyak, 2001; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Genus *Leptoglossus* Guérin-Ménéville, 1831

***Leptoglossus occidentalis* Heidemann, 1910**

Leptoglossus occidentalis Heidemann, 1910

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Eldivan, Gölezkayı entrance, 40°30'56"N, 33°32'32,7"E, 1022 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Amasya, Ankara, Balıkesir, Çorum, Edirne, İstanbul, İzmir (Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Çerçi & Koçak, 2016; Dursun, 2016; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021).

Genus *Syromastus* Berthold, 1827

***Syromastus rhombeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Cimex rhombeus Linnaeus, 1767; *Cimex quadratus* Fabricius, 1775; *Verlusia sinuata* Fieber, 1861; *Verlusia rhombea* var. *fusca* Vidal, 1936

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Atkaracalar, Budakpınar, Yakalı, 40°52'41"N, 33°00'30"E, 1265 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀; Bayramören, Boğazkaya, 40°59'26,7"N, 33°17'13"E, 1019 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀; Center, between Başegnez and Alanpınar, 40°43'52,4"N, 33°36'37,7"E, 956 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀, Haydarköy turnoff Alaçatı village, 40°31'25"N, 33°54'55"E, 704 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Çerkeş, return of Akbaş and Korakoca, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♀, between Yörük and Karakoca villages, 40°54'34,7"N, 32°5'40,3"E, 923 m, 20.VII.2014, ♀, ♂; Ilgaz, between Yenide-

mirçiler and Süleyman Hancılar, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀; Korgun, Maruf village exit, 40°38'19,1"N, 33°24'14,5"E, 1193 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀; Orta, Elmali, 40°32'27,2"N, 33°09'21,6"E, 1267 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀, Doğanlar village exit, 40°39'09"N, 33°10'18"E, 1315 m, 20.V.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, Demirsahan village exit, 40°24'58,7"N, 33°18'58"E, 906 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂; Yapraklı, Aşağıöz, 40°48'26,1"N, 33°54'41,6"E, 1144 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Amasya, Ankara, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bingöl, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Manisa, Nevşehir, Sivas, Sinop, Tokat, Van (Horváth, 1883, 1901; Hoberlandt, 1956; Linnavuori, 1965; Tuatay et al., 1972; Kıyak, 1990a, b; Gençer et al., 2004; Kıyak et al., 2004; Öz Saraç, 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Dursun, 2011b; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Subfamily Pseudophloeinae Stål, 1868

Genus *Coriomeris* Westwood, 1842

Coriomeris alpinus (Horváth, 1895)

Coreus alpinus Horváth, 1895; *Coriomeris alticola* Jakovlev, 1902; *Coriomeris scabricornis* var. *perlatus* Cerutti, 1937.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Aşağıçavuş village, 40°41'39,7"N, 33°38'01,7"E, 880 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, between Bakırlı and Karakocaş, 40°26'53,1"N, 33°21'33,4"E, 942 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Amasya, Ankara, Isparta (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Zengin & Dursun, 2019).

Coriomeris hirticornis (Fabricius, 1794)

Coreus hirticornis Fabricius, 1794; *Coreus hirsutus* Fieber, 1861; *Dasycoris dorsalis* Mulsant & Rey, 1870; *Coriomeris hirticornis* f. *burlinii* Mancini, 1959.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Dereçatı village, 40°44'57,0"N, 33°40'12,5"E, 1068 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♂; Çerkeş, Historic bridge, 40°54'16"N, 32°50'7"E, 949 m, 25.VIII.2013, ♀; İncügez village exit, 40°55'9,2"N, 32°58'35,3"E, 1103 m, 20.VII.2014, ♂, Kışla-Beymelik-Taşanlar-Tohumlar villages turnout, 40°54'33"N, 32°48'36"E, 1000 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♂; Şabanözü, Demirsahan village, 40°25'43,6" N, 33°17'38,1"E, 1035 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂, Mart village entrance, 40°25'16"N, 33°22'00"E, 910 m, 24.V.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, Buluca-İgdir turn left from the Bridge, 40°45'25,4"N, 33°47'7,24"E, 1195 m, 15.VII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Düzce, Elazığ, Erzurum, Giresun, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Konya, Malatya, Mersin, Muğla (Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Şerban, 2010; Fent, 2011; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Genus *Strobilotoma* Fieber, 1860

Strobilotoma typhaecornis (Fabricius, 1803)

Coreus typhaecornis Fabricius, 1803; *Coreus clavicornis* Fabricius, 1803; *Atractus*

genei Spinola, 1837; *Pseudophloeus obscurus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1840.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Between Pehlivanlı and Alaçatı villages, 40°34'19" N, 33°52'18"E, 925 m, 26.IV.2014, ♂; Orta, Elmalı entrance, 40°32'47,9"N, 33°9'7,9"E, 1280 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Bursa, Hatay, Isparta (Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012).

Family CYDNIDAE Billberg, 1820

Subfamily Cydninae Billberg, 1820

Genus *Macroscytus* Fieber, 1860

***Macroscytus brunneus* (Fabricius, 1803)**

Cydnus brunneus Fabricius, 1803; *Cydnus proximus* Rambur, 1839; *Aethus opacus* Stål, 1854; *Macroscytus scutellaris* Horváth, 1919; *Macroscytus exiguus* Horváth, 1919.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Tuzlu and Dede villages, 40°36'18"N, 33°40'36"E, 874 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Antalya, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Gaziantep, Hatay, Isparta (Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015b).

Subfamily Sehirinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus *Sehirus* Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Sehirus robustus* Horváth, 1895**

Sehirus robustus Horváth, 1895.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Çerkeş, Doğdu village, 40°53'15,4"N, 32°55'01,3"E, 1559 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Erzurum, Kars, Kayseri (Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı, 2015b).

Genus *Tritomegas* Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Tritomegas bicolor* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex bicolor Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex nubilosa* Harris, 1780; *Sehirus bicolor* var. *immaculatus* Royer, 1922; *Canthophorus bicolor* var. *kormilevi* Halászfy, 1954.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Çerkeş, between Türbaşı and Dağcukurören villages, 40°45'35"N, 32°50'19"E, 1220 m, 27.IV.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Ankara, Antalya, Edirne, Erzincan, Erzurum, İstanbul, Kastamonu, Kocaeli (Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaş, 2009; Kiyak & Akar, 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015b; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Family LYGAEIDAE Schilling, 1829

Subfamily Cyminae Baerensprung, 1850

Genus *Cymus* Hahn, 1832

***Cymus claviculus* (Fallén, 1807)**

Lygaeus claviculus Fallén, 1807; *Lygaeus caricis* Zetterstedt, 1828; *Cymus aridellus* Reuter, 1875.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Bayındır and Hasakça,

40°35'16,4"N, 33°49'10,7"E, 1104 m, 13.VIII.2014, 2 ♀♀, ♂; Kurşunlu, KöprülÜ, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.05.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Bartın, Çanakkale, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Zonguldak (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006).

Subfamily Geocorinae Dahlbom, 1851

Genus Geocoris Fallén, 1814

Subgenus Geocoris Fallén, 1814

Geocoris (Geocoris) ater (Fabricius, 1787)

Acanthia atra Fabricius, 1787; *Salda albipennis* Fabricius, 1803; *Ophthalmicus dispar* (non Waga): De Graaf et al., 1860; *Acanthia nigra* Walckenaer, 1802; *Lygaeus unistria* Latreille, 1804; *Salda stevenii* Lapeletier & Serville, 1825; *Ophthalmicus albobittatus* A. Costa, 1864; *Ophthalmicus albipennis* var. *costalis* Ferrari, 1874; *Ophthalmicus albipennis* var. *humeralis* Ferrari, 1874; *Ophthalmicus albipennis* var. *pallescens* Ferrari, 1874; *Geocoris albipennis* var. *ataenius* Puton in Puton & Noualhier, 1895; *Geocoris ater* f. *slovenica* Roubal, 1961.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Çerkeş, Kışla-Beymelik and Taşanlar-Tohumlar villages turnout, 40°54'33"N, 32°48'36"E, 1000 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀; Yapraklı, Aşağıöz, 40°48'26,1"N, 33°54'41,6"E, 1144 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Aksaray, Antalya, Çorum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Mersin, Kahramanmaraş, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Konya, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sinop, Yozgat (Lodos et al., 1999).

Subfamily Henestarinae Douglas & Scott, 1865

Genus Henestaris Spinola, 1837

Henestaris laticeps laticeps (Curtis, 1836)

Heterogaster laticeps Curtis, 1836; *Lygaeus lineola* Curtis, 1831; *Henestaris genei* Spinola, 1837; *Henestaris spinolae* A. Costa, 1839; *Henestaris hispanus* Rambur, 1839; *Heterogaster oculatus* Motschulsky, 1863; *Henestaris curtulus* Horváth, 1911; *Henestaris cypriacus* Wagner, 1949; *Henestaris oboussierae* Wagner, 1954.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kurşunlu, KöprülÜ, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, ♂.

Previous records: Antalya, Çanakkale, İzmir, Muğla (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Fent, 2011; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Subfamily Heterogastrinae Stål, 1862

Genus Heterogaster Schilling, 1829

Heterogaster affinis Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835

Heterogaster affinis Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Phygadeuon semicolon* Fieber, 1837; *Heterogaster affinis* var. *rubricatus* Puton, 1890.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Şabanözü, Şabanözü entrance, 40°30'20,4"N, 33°18'33,9"E, 1148 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀, Atkaracalar, Höyük village exit, 40°52'25,9"N, 33°03'36,2"E, 1378 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Bursa, Çankırı, Elazığ, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Nevşehir, Zonguldak (Tuatay et al., 1972; Lodos et al., 1999; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al.,

2006; Kiyak & Akar, 2010; Küçükbasmacı & Kiyak, 2015; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

***Heterogaster cathariae* (Geoffroy, 1785)**

Cimex cathariae Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex naevius* Gmelin, 1790; *Heterogaster rufescens* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Phygadeuonidae* Fieber, 1837; *Heterogaster bicolor* Kolenati, 1845; *Heterogaster nepetae* var. *cinnamomeus* Horváth, 1882; *Heterogaster xinjiangensis* Zou & Zheng, 1981.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Orta, İnkılap village, 40°34'48"N, 33°03' 41"E, 1290 m, 24.V.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Elazığ, Erzurum, Hatay, Gümüşhane, Kars, Mersin (Hoberlandt, 1956; Tuatay et al., 1972; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yazıcı, 2022b).

***Heterogaster urticae* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Cimex urticae Fabricius, 1775; *Heterogaster notatipes* Walker, 1872; *Heterogaster longirostris* Wagner, 1949.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Orta, Hasanahacı village entrance, 40°35'38,4"N, 33°2'59,9"E, 1291 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂; Şabanözü, Demirsahan, 40°25'22"N, 33°17'35"E, 1004 m, 11.VII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Aksaray, Antalya, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bartın, Bayburt, Bolu, Bursa, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Mersin, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Trabzon, Zonguldak (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Subfamily Lygaeinae Schilling, 1829

Genus *Horvathiolus* Josifov, 1965

***Horvathiolus superbus* (Pollich, 1781)**

Cimex superbus Pollich, 1781; *Cimex punctatoguttatus* Fabricius, 1781; *Cimex discolor* Gmelin, 1790; *Lygaeus schummelii* Schilling, 1829; *Lygaeus superbus* var. *melanogaster* Horváth, 1899; *Melanocoryphus confluens* Horváth, 1916; *Melanocoryphus sanctus* Horváth, 1916; *Melanocoryphus superbus* var. *kolenatii* Horváth, 1916; *Melanocoryphus superbus* var. *erythropus* Horváth, 1916; *Spilostethus superbus* var. *conjunctus* Mancini, 1952.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, Kemalli village entrance, 40°18'6"N, 34°02'37"E, 686 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀;

Previous records: Antalya, Balıkesir, Bolu, Isparta, Karaman, Kırıkkale, Kilis, Konya, Mersin (Lodos et al., 1999; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Dursun, 2016).

Genus *Lygaeosoma* Spinola, 1837

***Lygaeosoma anatolicum* Seidenstücker, 1960**

Lygaeosoma anatolicum Seidenstücker, 1960.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Erzurum, Kırıkkale, Konya (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006;

Çerçi et al., 2022).

***Lygaeosoma sardeum sardeum* Spinola, 1837**

Lygaeosoma sardea Spinola, 1837; *Heterogaster reticulatus* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838; *Pachymerus variabilis* Rambur, 1839; *Lygaeosoma reticulatum* var. *numidicum* Puton, 1887; *Lygaeosoma reticulatum* f. *hungarica* Stichel, 1957.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Ilgaz, Kale village, 40°57'12,3"N, 33°39'12,2"E, 980 m, 17.VII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Bingöl, Çanakkale (Şerban, 2010; Çerçi et al., 2018).

Genus *Melanocoryphus* Stål, 1872

***Melanocoryphus albomaculatus* (Goeze, 1778)**

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Atkaracalar, Ilıksu, 40°48'6,8"N, 33°05'48,4"E, 1207 m, 20.VII.2014, ♀; Center, between Karadayı and Külburun, 40°24'41"N, 33°45'27"E, 843 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, between Tuzlu and Dede villages, 40°36'18"N, 33°40'36"E, 874 m, 26.O4.2014, ♀; Orta, Sakaeli exit, 40°40'19"N, 33°09'48"E, 1227 m, 21.V.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Korgun, Karatepe (Şihlar) village, 40°46'58,8"N, 33°32'4"E, 1019 m, 16.VII.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Köprülü, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.V.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bursa, Çankırı, Çorum, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Isparta, İzmir, Karabük, Kars, Malatya, Zonguldak (Tuatay et al., 1972; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Özgen et al., 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Subfamily Orsillinae Stål, 1872

Genus *Nysius* Dallas, 1852

***Nysius cymoides* (Spinola, 1837)**

Artheneis cymoides Spinola, 1837; *Nysius albidus* Dallas, 1852; *Heterogaster exilis* A. Costa, 1853; *Nysius fuliginosus* Fieber, 1861; *Nysius thoracicus* Horváth, 1882.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Dereçatı village, 40°44'57,0" N, 33°40'12,5"E, 1068 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♂, Haydarköy turnoff Alaçatı village, 40°31'25"N, 33°54'55"E, 704 m, 26.IV.2014, 4 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, between Pehlivanlı and Alaçatı villages, 40°34'19" N, 33°52'18"E, 925 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, between Korçullu and Kenallı villages, 40°18'43,0"N, 34°00'38"E, 557 m, 12.VIII.2014, ♂, Kuzeykişla entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, between Yukarıalagöz and Alaca villages, 40°22'28"N, 33°54'54"E, 619 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Şabanözü, Mart village entrance, 40°25'16"N, 33°22'00"E, 910 m, 24.V.2014, ♂; highland road between Maruf and Kamış, 40°34'43,9"N, 33°21'7,2"E, 1431 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♂; Yapraklı, Buluca and İğdir turn left from the bridge, 40°45'25,4"N, 33°47'7,24"E, 1195 m, 15.VII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Aksaray, Artvin, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Burdur, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Kırşehir, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Nevşehir, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ, Tokat, Yalova, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Yazıcı, 2022a, b).

Subfamily Oxycareninae Stål, 1862**Genus Oxycarenus Fieber, 1837****Subgenus Euoxycarenus Samy, 1969*****Oxycarenus (Euoxycarenus) pallens* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850)**

Stenogaster pallens Herrich-Schaeffer, 1850; *Stenogaster collaris* Mulsant & Rey, 1852; *Oxycarenus luteolus* Hoberlandt, 1943; *Oxycarenus longiceps* Wagner, 1955.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Şabanözü, Demirsahan village exit, 40°24'58,7"N, 33°18'58"E, 906 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bolu, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırıkkale, Kırşehir, Kilis, Konya, Nevşehir, Mardin, Mersin, Nevşehir, Niğde, Sinop, Sivas, Zonguldak (Tuatay et al., 1972; Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Kıyak et al., 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Subgenus Oxycarenus Fieber, 1837***Oxycarenus (Oxycarenus) hyalinipennis* (A. Costa, 1843)**

Aphanus tardus var. *hyalinipennis* A. Costa, 1843; *Oxycarenus leucopterus* Fieber, 1851; *Oxycarenus cruralis* Stål, 1856; *Cymus cincticornis* Walker, 1870; *Oxycarenus castaneus* Bergevin, 1932.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Haydarköy turnoff alaçat village, 40°31'25"N, 33°54'55"E, 704 m, 26.IV.2014, ♀, 3 ♂♂; Kızılırmak, Karallı village, 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂, Kuzeykışla entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀; Kurşunlu, between Sünürlü and Sakaeli, 40°42'01"N, 33°08'53"E, 1415 m, 21.V.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Antalya, Çanakkale, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul, İzmir, Karaman, Kastamonu, Kilis, Konya, Mersin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Sinop (Aysev, 1974; Lodos et al., 1999; Şerban, 2010; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Subfamily Rhyparochrominae Amyot & Serville, 1843**Genus Beosus Amyot & Serville, 1843*****Beosus quadripunctatus* (Müller, 1766)**

Cimex quadripunctatus Müller, 1766; *Aphanus erythropterus* Brullé, 1832; *Pachymerus pulcher* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835; *Pachymerus ibericus* Kolenati, 1845; *Beosus quadripunctatus* var. *ochraceus* Wagner, 1949.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Balıbağı highland, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, between Bayındır and Hasakça, 40°35'16,4"N, 33°49'10,7"E, 1104 m, 13.VIII.2014, ♂, Dereçatı village, 40°44'57,0" N, 33°40'12,5"E, 1068 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀; between Karadayı and Külburun, 40°24'41"N, 33°45'27"E, 843 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Çerkeş, Return of Akbaş and Korakoca, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Köpürlü exit, 40°46'41,1"N, 33°16'57,9"E, 1068 m, 06.VIII.2014, ♀, 2 ♂♂; Şabanözü, between Bakırlı and Karakoçaş, 40°26'53,1"N, 33°21'33,4"E, 942 m, 08.VIII.2014, ♀, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Bartın, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çorum, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Gaziantep, Hatay, Iğdır,

İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Karabük, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Karaman, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Muğla, Niğde, Osmaniye, Yalova, Zonguldak (Hoherlandt, 1956; Tuatay et al., 1972; Aysev, 1974; Önder et al., 1984; Lodos et al., 1999; Fent, 2011; Matocq et al., 2014; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Çerçi et al., 2018; Özgen et al., 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b, c; Çerçi et al., 2022).

Genus *Graptopeltus* Stål, 1872

***Graptopeltus lynceus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Cimex lynceus Fabricius, 1775; *Cimex collinus* (non Scopoli, 1763): Schrank, 1781.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Kemalli village entrance, 40°18'6"N, 34°02'37"E, 686 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Isparta, Kahramanmaraş, Tunceli (Lodos et al., 1999; Fent & Japoshvili, 2012; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus *Raglius* Stål, 1872

***Raglius confusus* (Reuter, 1886)**

Pachymerus confusus Reuter, 1886; *Cimex triguttatus* (non Linnaeus, 1767): Fabricius, 1775; *Rhyparochromus pineti* (non Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835): Fieber, 1861; *Pachymerus confusus* var. *nigripes* Puton in Reuter, 1886.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Bayramören, between Çatkase and Başovacık, 40°53'29,1"N, 33°12'14,4"E, 1226 m, 22.VIII.2014, ♂; Eldivan, Eldivan mountain, 40°30'24,5"N, 33°30'28"E, 1132 m, 11.VII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Kuzeykışla entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, between Yukarıalagöz and Alaca villages, 40°22'28"N, 33°54'54"E, 619 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂; Orta, Doğanlar village exit, 40°39'09"N, 33°10'18"E, 1315 m, 20.V.2014, 2 ♀♀, ♂, Elmalı, 40°32'27,2"N, 33°09'21,6"E, 1267 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Balıkesir, Bursa, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, İstanbul, Kars, Muğla, Tunceli (Aysev, 1974; Yazıcı et al., 2015a; Dursun, 2016).

Genus *Rhyparochromus* Hahn, 1826

***Rhyparochromus pini* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex pini Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex collinus* Scopoli, 1763; *Cimex circuluspunctatus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex crucifer* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex circulus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex collium* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex sylvaticus* (non Fabricius, 1775): Cederhjelms, 1798.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Tuzlu and Dede villages, 40°36'18"N, 33°40'36"E, 874 m, 26.IV.2014, 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ankara, Bursa, Erzincan, Erzurum, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kastamonu, Mersin (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus *Scolopostethus* Fieber, 1860

***Scolopostethus affinis* (Schilling, 1829)**

Pachymerus affinis Schilling, 1829; *Lygaeus podagricus* var. β (non Fabricius, 1775): Fallén, 1829; *Pachymerus pictus* (non Schilling, 1829): Herrich-Schaeffer, 1833; *Scolopostethus adjunctus* Douglas & Scott, 1865.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kurşunlu, Dağören village, 40°46'54"N,

33°14'27"E, 1283 m, 21.V.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Antalya, Bolu, Erzurum, Hatay, İzmir, Karaman, Konya, Nevşehir, Sinop, Sivas, Zonguldak (Lodos et al., 1999; Önder et al., 2006; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Genus *Xanthochilus* Stål, 1872

***Xanthochilus quadratus* (Fabricius, 1798)**

Lygaeus quadratus Fabricius, 1798; *Aphanus quadratus* var. *immaculatus* Royer, 1919; *Aphanus brevirostris* Ribaut, 1921; *Rhyparochromus* (*Neoxanthochilus*) *quadratus interruptus* Wagner, 1956.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Eldivan, Gölezkayı entrance, 40°30'56"N, 33°32'32,7"E, 1022 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀; Korgun, Sanı Highland, 40°37'00"N, 33°24'10"E, 1363 m, 20.V.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Ankara, Antalya, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bursa, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, Kars, Kayseri, Mersin (Önder et al., 2006; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Fent, 2011; Yazıcı et al., 2015a).

Family NABIDAE A. Costa, 1853

Subfamily Nabinae A. Costa, 1853

Genus *Himacerus* Wolff, 1811

Subgenus *Aptus* Hahn, 1831

***Himacerus (Aptus) mirmicoides* (O. Costa, 1834)**

Nabis mirmicoides O. Costa, 1834; *Aptus apterus* (non Fabricius, 1798): Hahn, 1831; *Nabis subapterus* (non De Geer, 1773): Burmeister, 1835; *Nabis lativentris* Boheman, 1852; *Nabis lativentris* var. *fulvus* Rey, 1893; *Nabis lativentris* var. *femoralis* Rey, 1893.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Ilgaz, between Çaltıpınar and Ödemiş, 40°56'46,9"N, 33°33'40,5"E, 996 m, 18.VII.2014, ♀, Yuvasaray exit first km towards Yukarıöz, 40°53'12"N, 33°42'56"E, 894 m, 25.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Ağrı, Ankara, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bursa, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Giresun, Gümüşhane, Kastamonu, Ordu, Tokat (Linnavuori, 1965; Önder et al., 1984; Gençer et al., 2004; Dursun, 2011a; Dursun, 2016; Dursun & Fent, 2016; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Matocq et al., 2014; Asal, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yazıcı, 2022c; Yazıcı, 2023).

Genus *Nabis* Latreille, 1802

Subgenus *Nabis* Latreille, 1802

***Nabis (Nabis) ferus ferus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex ferus Linnaeus, 1758; *Cimex tripunctatus* Müller, 1776; *Cimex scutellomaculatus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex marginatostratus* Goeze, 1778; *Cimex sponsalis* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785; *Cimex vagans* Fabricius, 1787; *Cimex triops* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex sexstriatus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex denigratus* Gmelin, 1790; *Cimex heraldicus* Schrank, 1801; *Reduvius pallens* Panzer, 1804; *Cimex cinereus* Olivier, 1811.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Center, Balıbağı highland, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂; Kurşunlu, Dağören village, 40°46'54"N, 33°14'27"E, 1283 m, 21.V.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, Aşağıöz, 40°48'26,1"N, 33°54'41,6"E, 1144 m, 25.VIII.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adana, Ağrı, Aksaray, Amasya, Ankara, Antalya, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Giresun, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kars, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Mardin, Mersin, Niğde, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Trabzon (Kiyak, 1990; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2011a; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Kaplan, 2014; Asal 2015; Yazıcı, 2023).

***Nabis (Nabis) punctatus punctatus* A. Costa, 1847**

Nabis punctatus A. Costa, 1847; *Nabis agilis* Spinola, 1837; *Nabis feroides* Remane, 1953.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, Aşağıçavuş village, 40°41'39,7"N, 33°38'01,7"E, 880 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, ♂, Balıbağı highland, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, Kızılırmak, Bozkır village exit, 40°26'54,3"N, 33°49'25"E, 1637 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♀, Karallı village, 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀, Kuzeykişla entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, ♂; Korgun, Akçavakıf, 40°41'35,5"N, 33°34'18,2"E, 824 m, 15.VII.2014, 4 ♀♀, ♂; Orta, between Elmalı and Kayılar, 40°32'14"N, 33°06'35,4"E, 1370 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀, Elmalı entrance, 40°32'47,9"N, 33°9'7,9"E, 1280 m, 07.VIII.2014, ♂; Şabanözü, Çaparkayı, 40°31'22,3"N, 33°21'12,3"E, 1229 m, 11.VII.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, Bugay Village entrance, 40°41'5,6"N, 33°46'32,7"E, 897 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, Yakadere, 40°41'25"N, 33°48'56"E, 1030 m, 24.VII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Adıyaman, Afyonkarahisar, Amasya, Ankara, Batman, Burdur, Bursa, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Giresun, Iğdır, Isparta, İzmir, Karaman, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Konya, Malatya, Mardin, Niğde, Şanlıurfa, Siirt, Sivas, Şanlıurfa, Tokat, Van, Yozgat, Zonguldak (Gençer et al., 2004; Dursun, 2011a; Yıldırım et al., 2013; Kaplan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Asal, 2015; Yıldırım et al., 2013a; Bolu, 2020).

Family PIESMATIDAE Amyot and Serville, 1843

Genus *Piesma* Lepeletier & Serville, 1828

***Piesma maculatum* (Laporte, 1833)**

Zosmenus maculatus Laporte, 1833; *Tingis capitatum* (non Wolff, 1804): Fallén, 1807; *Zosmenus laportei* Fieber, 1844; *Zosmenus viridis* Jakovlev, 1871.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Korgun, Sanı highland, 40°37'00"N, 33°24'10"E, 1363 m, 20.V.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Balıkesir, Erzurum (Yıldırım & Özbek, 1990; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2013b).

Family REDUVIDAE Latreille, 1807

Subfamily Harpactorinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus *Coranus* Curtis, 1833

***Coranus (Coranus) kerzhneri* P.V. Putshkov, 1982**

Coranus kerzhneri P.V. Putshkov, 1982; *Coranus tuberculifer* (non Reuter, 1881): Kerzhner in Kerzhner & Jaczewski, 1964; *Coranus subapterus* (non De Geer, 1773): Benedek, 1969; *Coranus subapterus* (non De Geer, 1773): Önder, 1980.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Halimintepe exit Karamursel village, 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Amasya, Çanakkale, Edirne, Erzurum, Manisa, Muğla, Tunceli

(Yıldırım et al., 2010, 2013a; Asal, 2015).

Genus *Nagusta* Stål, 1859

Nagusta goedelii (Kolenati, 1857)

Zelus goedelii Kolenati, 1857; *Nagusta rugulosa* Stål, 1859; *Phanerochoris cornutus* Jakovlev, 1876.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Bayramören, between Çayırcık and Evkadı, 41°2'8"N, 33°9'28"E, 1000 m, 27.VIII.2013, ♂; Center, between Başegnez and Alanpınar, 40°43'52,4"N, 33°36'37,7"E, 956 m, 09.VIII.2014, ♀; Çerkeş, between Dodurga and Karacahöyük, 40°56'34"N, 33°0'52"E, 1023 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♀.

Previous records: Amasya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Çanakkale, Çankırı, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, İstanbul, İzmir, Kars, Malatya, Mardin, Sivas, Tokat (Çam, 1993; Yıldırım et al., 2010, 2013a; Dursun, 2011a; Fent, 2011; Kaplan, 2014; Matocq et al., 2014; Asal, 2015; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi et al., 2018; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021).

Subfamily Phymatinae Laporte, 1832

Genus *Phymata* Latreille, 1802

Subgenus *Phymata* Latreille, 1802

Phymata (Phymata) crassipes (Fabricius, 1775)

Acanthia crassipes Fabricius, 1775; *Cimex chelifer* Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Kızılırmak, Karallı village, 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Amasya, Ankara, Bilecik, Kocaeli, Sakarya, Sivas, Tokat, Zonguldak (Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun, 2011a).

Family RHOPALIDAE Amyot & Serville, 1843

Subfamily Rhopalinae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Genus *Brachycarenum* Fieber, 1860

Brachycarenum tigrinus (Schilling, 1829)

Rhopalus tigrinus Schilling, 1829; *Corisus pudicus* Rambur, 1839; *Corizus laticeps* Boheman, 1851; *Corizus gemmatus* A. Costa, 1853; *Heterogaster punctosus* Walker, 1872.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Center, Aşağıçavuş village, 40°41'39,7"N, 33°38'01,7"E, 880 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀, Haydarköy turnoff Alaçatı village, 40°31'25"N, 33°54'55"E, 704 m, 26.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, Balıbağı highland, 40°29'50"N, 33°52'42"E, 774 m, 25.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, between Karadayı and Külburun, 40°24'41"N, 33°45'27"E, 843 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Çerkeş, return of Akbaş and Korakoca, 40°54'55,9"N, 32°53'04,4"E, 912 m, 21.VIII.2014, ♀, Doğdu village, 40°53'15,4"N, 32°55'01,3"E, 1559 m, 19.VIII.2014, ♀, Kışla-Beymelik-Taşanlar-Tohumlar villages turnout, 40°54'33"N, 32°48'36"E, 1000 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♂; Ilgaz, Kırışlılar, 40°55'46,1"N, 33°29'22,5"E, 1025 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀, Yuvasaray village exit fourth km from Yukariöz, 40°52'8"N, 33°46'27"E, 1101 m, 25.VII.2013, ♂; Kızılırmak, between Boyacıoğlu and Karamürsel, 40°25'36"N, 34°02'19"E, 543 m, 24.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, 3 ♂♂, Center, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 25.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, Halimintepe exit Karamürsel village, 40°24'06"N, 34°02'26"E, 550 m, 24.IV.2014, 2 ♂♂, between Pehlivanlı and Alaçatı villages, 40°34'19" N, 33°52'18"E, 925 m,

26.IV.2014, ♀, 3 ♂♂, Karallı village, 40°18'30"N, 33°56'36"E, 606 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, 3 ♀♀, 10 ♂♂; Kurşunlu, Dumanlı village exit, 40°40'31"N, 33°13'45"E, 1403 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, ♂, Köprülü, 40°50'29"N, 33°15'38"E, 1130 m, 20.V.2014, ♀, between Köprülü and Kapaklı, 40°45'11"N, 33°16'31"E, 1329 m, 20.V.2014, ♂, between Sünürlü and Sakaeli, 40°42'01"N, 33°08'53"E, 1415 m, 21.V.2014, ♂; Orta, Sakaeli exit, 40°40'19"N, 33°09'48"E, 1227 m, 21.V.2014, ♀; Yapraklı, Bugay village entrance, 40°41'5,6"N, 33°46'32,7"E, 897 m, 15.VII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Bozkır village exit, 40°26'54,3"N, 33°49'25"E, 1637 m, 11.VIII.2014, ♂, Buluca-İğdir turn left from the bridge, 40°45'25,4"N, 33°47'7,24"E, 1195 m, 15.VII.2014, 2 ♀♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Amasya, Ankara, Aydın, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Çanakkale, Çorum, Denizli, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Iğdır, İstanbul, Karabük, Kars, Kastamonu, Kayseri, Kırşehir, Malatya, Nevşehir, Yozgat (Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 1984; Kıyak et al., 2004; Abacıgil et al., 2010; Şerban, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014; Dursun, 2016; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Çerçi et al., 2022; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Genus *Chorosoma* Curtis, 1830

Chorosoma schillingii (Schilling, 1829)

Rhopalus schillingii Schilling, 1829; *Chorosoma arundinis* Curtis, 1830; *Chorosoma punctipes* Fieber, 1870; *Chorosoma schillingii* var. *nigrescens* Cohrs, 1934.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Amasya, Ankara, Çankırı, Diyarbakır, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Isparta, Kayseri, Mardin, Muş, Nevşehir, Sinop (Kıyak et al., 2004; Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011; Matocq et al., 2014; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Akman & Dursun, 2021; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Genus *Maccevethus* Dallas, 1852

Maccevethus caucasicus (Kolenati, 1845)

Corizus caucasicus Kolenati, 1845; *Stictopleurus elongatus* Blöte, 1934; *Maccevethus houskai* Hoberlandt, 1952.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Karadayı and Külburun, 40°24'41"N, 33°45'27"E, 843 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀; Ilgaz, between Yenidemirciler and Süleyman Hancılar, 40°54'48,2"N, 33°30'13,7"E, 983 m, 19.VII.2014, ♀; Kızılırmak, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Adıyaman, Ankara, Artvin, Çankırı, Elazığ, Erzincan, Erzurum, Eskişehir, Iğdır, Kars, Kayseri, Yozgat (Kıyak & Akar, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2011, 2013b; Küçükbasmacı & Kıyak, 2015; Çerçi & Özgen, 2021; Kıyak & Baş, 2021).

Genus *Stictopleurus* Stål, 1872

Stictopleurus subtomentosus (Rey, 1888)

Corizus subtomentosus Rey, 1888; *Stictopleurus riveti* Royer, 1923; *Stictopleurus parvus* Lindberg, 1948; *Stictopleurus riveti* f. *flaveola* Tamanini, 1951.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Cacıklar, 40°23'43"N, 34°04'18"E, 597 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m,

24.IV.2014, ♂, between Yukarıalagöz and Alaca villages, 40°22'28"N, 33°54'54"E, 619 m, 25.IV.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Diyarbakir, Elazığ, Erzurum, Hakkari, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Van (Önder et al., 2006; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Matocq et al., 2014).

***Stictopleurus unicolor* (Jakovlev, 1873)**

Rhopalus unicolor Jakovlev, 1873.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kızılırmak, Kuzeykışla entrance, 40°22'14"N, 34°03'00"E, 600 m, 24.IV.2014, ♂, Tepealagöz village exit, 40°21'49"N, 34°00'56"E, 557 m, 24.IV.2014, ♀, ♂; Orta, Sakaeli exit, 40°40'19"N, 33°09'48"E, 1227 m, 21.V.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Bartın, Erzurum, Kars (Hoberlandt, 1956; Önder et al., 2006; Yıldırım et al., 2013b; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Family SCUTELLERIDAE Leach, 1815

Subfamily Odontotarsinae Mulsant & Rey, 1865

Genus *Odontotarsus* Laporte, 1833

***Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Cimex purpureolineatus Rossi, 1790; *Odontotarsus grammicus* [var.] *lutescens* Fieber, 1861; *Odontotarsus rugicollis* Jakovlev, 1884; *Odontotarsus insignis* Jakovlev, 1908; *Odontotarsus purpureolineatus* f. *confluens* Hoberlandt, 1944.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Center, between Karadayı and Külburun, 40°24'41"N, 33°45'27"E, 843 m, 25.IV.2014, ♀.

Previous records: Adana, Adıyaman, Ankara, Antalya, Artvin, Balıkesir, Bayburt, Bilecik, Bursa, Çanakkale, Diyarbakır, Edirne, Erzurum, Gaziantep, Iğdır, Isparta, İstanbul, İzmir, Kahramanmaraş, Kars, Kayseri, Kırklareli, Konya, Mersin, Muş, Rize, Siirt, Şanlıurfa, Şırnak, Tekirdağ (Tuatay et al., 1972; Önder et al., 2006; Fent & Aktaç, 2009; Şerban, 2010; Yıldırım et al., 2014; Yazıcı, 2022b).

Family TINGIDAE Laporte, 1832

Subfamily Tinginae Laporte, 1832

Genus *Copium* Thunberg, 1822

***Copium clavicorne clavicorne* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Cimex clavicornis Linnaeus, 1758; *Tingis punctata* Lamarck, 1816; *Copium cornutum* Thunberg, 1822; *Eurycera nigricornis* Laporte, 1833.

Material examined: Çankırı prov.: Kurşunlu, Dumanlı village exit, 40°40'31"N, 33°13'45"E, 1403 m, 20.V.2014, ♂; Orta, Dodurga, 40°36'11"N, 33°00'18"E, 1351 m, 22.V.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Bartın, Bursa, Çanakkale, Kastamonu, Tekirdağ (Önder et al., 2006; Fent, 2011; Küçükbasmacı, 2014; Küçükbasmacı et al., 2016; Dursun & Fent, 2017; Yazıcı, 2022c).

Genus *Corythucha* Stål, 1873

***Corythucha ciliata* (Say, 1832)**

Tingis ciliata Say, 1832; *Tingis hyalina* Herrich-Schaeffer, 1842.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Çerkeş, Kışla-Beymelik-Taşanlar-Tohumlar villages turnout, 40°54'33"N, 32°48'36"E, 1000 m, 26.VIII.2013, ♂; Çerkeş, between Dodurga and Çakmak villages, 40°56'54"N, 33°1'42"E, 1232 m, 27.VIII.2013, 2 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂; Çerkeş, between Dodurga and Karacahöyük, 40°56'34"N, 33°0'52"E, 1023 m, 26.VIII.2013, 2 ♀♀, ♂; Orta, between Çerçi and Elmalı, 40°32'09,6"N, 33°10'31,3"E, 1227 m, 08.VII.2014, ♀, ♂.

Previous records: Bursa, Kastamonu (Küçükbaşmacı, 2014; Küçükbaşmacı et al., 2016; Çerçi et al., 2021).

Genus *Physatocheila* Fieber, 1844

Physatocheila dumetorum (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838)

Monanthia dumetorum Herrich-Schaeffer, 1838; *Tingis oxyacanthae* Curtis, 1839.

Material examined: **Çankırı prov.:** Çerkeş, Türbaşı village turnout, 40°47'09"N, 34°51'43"E, 626 m, 27.IV.2014, ♂.

Previous records: Ankara, Erzincan, Erzurum, Kars, Tokat, Van (Çam, 1993; Atlıhan et al., 2011; Yıldırım et al., 2013a).

DISCUSSION and CONCLUSION

In this study, the research material consists of samples collected from 108 different localities in around Çankırı province between 2013 and 2014. As a result of the determination of the material collected in Çankırı province, 48 species belonging to 41 genera from 11 families (Anthocoridae, Berytidae, Coreidae, Cydnidae, Lygaeidae, Nabidae, Piesmatidae, Reduviidae, Rhopalidae, Scutelleridae, Tingidae). 38 of these species are reported for the first time Heteroptera fauna of Çankırı.

Species recored from Çankırı belong to 11 families (Table 1). Majority of them belong to families Lygaeidae (33%, 80 samples), Rhopalidae (26%, 63 samples) and Coreidae (18%, 44 samples). Berytidae (0%, 1 sample), Piesmatidae (0%, 1 sample), Scutelleridae (0%,1 sample) were under-represented in the Heteroptera fauna of Çankırı when compared to Turkish fauna. Underrepresentation of these families are probably due to methods that we used to collect specimens.

Table 1. Number of species recorded from Çankırı, sorted into families.

Çankırı is a transition region between Central Anatolia and Black Sea Region of Turkey. Therefore, in this transition area the diversity and abundance of insects is more because of is abundant variety of plants. The high number of species obtained from Çankırı is also due to this reason. In addition, the high number of newly recorded species from Çankırı is a result of lack of adequate studies in the past. These findings strongly suggest that Çankırı province possesses a species rich Heteroptera fauna which, even after this study, remains to be fully uncovered.

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